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Pumped hydropower storage in closed open-pit lignite mines can provide substantial contributions to the European energy transition

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ABSTRACT

Decommissioning lignite mines supports the European Union's (EU) climate targets of 55% net greenhouse gas reduction by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050. One way to reach these objectives is by increasing the share of renewables in the energy mix. However, increasing the share of variable renewable energy requires flexible and scalable storage. Transforming decommissioned open-pit lignite mines into Pumped Hydropower Storage (PHS) sites offers a solution that enhances energy security while enabling regional economic transition. Multiple lignite mines have been decommissioned or scheduled for closure between 2038 and 2045. Prior studies on utility-scale storage focused primarily on existing reservoirs, with only a limited number exploring the potential of open-pit mines. The present study evaluated 164 EU open-pit lignite mines and identified 50 technically feasible sites for PHS implementation. Two scenarios incorporating assumptions focusing on load balancing and demand management were assessed. Maximising power capacity for short-term load balancing yielded 9.6 GW power and 117 GWh storage, representing approximately 21% of current EU installed PHS capacity and a 45% storage increase. In contrast, maximising energy storage for seasonal demand resulted in lower power capacity of 5.4 GW (12% of EU total) but significantly higher storage capacity of 13 TWh, a 4,860% increase. These findings highlight the substantial potential of utilising closed open-pit lignite mines for PHS to support the EU's energy transition, directly aligning with the EU Green Deal and energy security objectives by a utility-scale solution that optimises renewable energy capacity utilisation.

Introduction

Decommissioning lignite mines is a strategic pillar of the European Green Deal, aiming for 55% net greenhouse gas emissions reduction by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050 [1]. EU member states have developed national strategies to support these goals, including replacing coal-based energy with renewable sources comprising 69% and 80% of the energy mix by 2030 and 2050, respectively [2]. Climate goals, energy security, economic diversification and environmental concerns are the key drivers for this transition. The European Commission has implemented various initiatives and support mechanisms to facilitate the transition, including the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM), the Coal Regions in Transition Initiative and European Union Funding programs to provide assistance and support sustainability [3–5].

Current status of coal industry in Europe

The end dates for decommissioning of lignite mines as a way to decarbonise the energy sector have been set and the transition process has started in the EU member states. In 2023, the consumption of lignite within the EU decreased, representing a significant decline of 40% in comparison to 2018, thereby reaching the lowest recorded level. Production patterns exhibit a close correlation with consumption, as lignite is predominantly used in the countries where it is mined [6]. This downward trajectory in the consumption and production of coal within the EU is attributable to several key factors that rendered its utilisation increasingly unappealing [7]. The Kyoto Protocol [8], in conjunction with the implementation of the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) as part of the EU's enhanced environmental policies [9], has significantly influenced the economic viability of coal, characterised by high carbon emissions. Carbon pricing under the EU ETS has reduced coal's competitiveness as allowance prices increased from EUR 25 in 2020 to EUR 84 in 2023, representing a 236% growth [10]. This

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Nomenclature		η	Efficiency (%)
Abbreviations		P	Power (MW)
CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage	Q	Volumetric flow (m ³ /s)
DEM	Digital Elevation Model	μ	Kinematic viscosity of water (m ² /s)
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System	v	Flow velocity (m/s)
GIS	Geographic Information System	$V_{\text{reservoir}}$	Volume of the upper reservoir
GHG	Greenhouse Gas	Units	
PHS	Pumped Hydropower Storage	GWh	Gigawatt-hour
PV	Photovoltaic	GW	Gigawatt
vRES	Variable Renewable Energy Sources	kg	Kilogram
Symbols		kg/m ³	Kilogram per cubic meter
D	Penstock diameter (m)	km ²	Square kilometer
Δh	Hydraulic head difference (m)	m	Meter
E_{PHS}	Energy that can potentially be stored (GWh)	m ²	Square meter
ϵ	Effective roughness of the penstock wall (–)	m ³	Cubic meter
f_D	Darcy friction factor (–)	m ³ /s	Cubic meter per second
g	Gravitational acceleration (m/s ²)	Mt	Megatonne
h_f	Head loss (m)	MW	Megawatt
L	Penstock length (m)	MWh	Megawatt-hour

shift reflects the EU's transition towards a more sustainable energy framework aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and achieving climate neutrality.

Importance of shifting from fossil fuel towards clean energy by 2050

European and OECD countries are required to eliminate coal dependency by 2030 at the latest [11] to conform to the stipulations of the United Nations Paris Climate Agreement [12]. Most EU member states have successfully achieved this goal, with a few exceptions that remain significantly reliant on coal and timelines extending beyond 2030. For instance, lignite coal mines in Germany and Poland are projected to cease operations the latest by 2038 and 2040, respectively [2]. The need for utility-scale energy storage increases with power production from renewable energy sources. More storage projects are required to increase the currently available share of renewables to support meeting the EU targets [13] as presented in Fig. 1. Additionally, flexibility in storage also needs to greatly increase to accommodate higher shares of renewables in the energy mix. In this context, repurposing of open-pit lignite mines into Pumped Hydropower Storage (PHS) installations for excess energy storage from the electric grid and local renewable sources can contribute to energy supply security and facilitate the overall

transition process. The concept of PHS in closed open-pit lignite mines is based on using the existing mining pit as lower PHS reservoir, while the upper reservoir is constructed outside of the open pit to store energy in the form of gravitational potential energy [14,15]. Both reservoirs are connected via penstocks with powerhouse facilities equipped with turbines, and via transformers to the electric grid [16].

PHS capacities in view of utility-scale battery storage

PHS accounts for the highest portion of global storage capacities at the large-scale with 179 GW, followed by utility-scale battery storage with 28 GW [18,19]. Both technologies expanded significantly in 2022 with PHS capacity increasing by 10.5 GW and battery storage by 11 GW [20]. The latter is experiencing a markedly rapid expansion, despite commencing from a comparatively low base. Although battery technology is regarded as an essential solution for reducing grid dependency and providing backup power, [21] highlights that its production in Europe is projected to result in substantial environmental impacts. On the other hand, PHS is a well established, reliable and flexible energy storage technology that is widely used for load balancing and demand management. It is particularly effective in storing surplus energy from the electric grid, including intermittent renewable sources such as wind and solar power. Within the EU, PHS has a total installed power capacity of 46 GW, accounting for approximately one-fourth of the global installed capacity. Globally, China leads with an installed PHS capacity of about 51 GW [15].

Studies show that besides the fast development of large-scale battery storage systems [20,22] with approximately 5 GW of installed capacity in 2021 within the EU [23], PHS will remain the key technology for energy storage at the utility scale. The globally installed PHS storage capacity of 179 GW is anticipated to be extended by about 56% to exceed 270 GW by 2030 [18,24,25], maintaining its lead over battery systems, even when including electric vehicle batteries [20]. EU average round-trip efficiencies of up to 71% [15] and extraordinary high storage capacities compared to utility-scale battery-based solutions can be realised. Although PHS is currently the only utility-scale energy storage technology at full maturity, its potential is still limited by the availability of sites and varies considerably from one country to another [26]. Addressing this constraint, [27] identified potential global greenfield (newly developed sites) and bluefield (existing sites adapted for new purposes) sites including locations in Europe and ranked them into cost

Fig. 1. EU energy storage (PHS, batteries and other sources) and power capacity for 2022 and targets for 2030–2050 [17].

classes based on suitability. Classes A, AA and AAA represent the most suitable sites with minimum costs. While most of the EU member states have significant numbers of Class A–AAA greenfield and bluefield PHS sites [27,28], their development in the EU is hindered by strong public opposition, environmental regulations, and permitting delays [29–31]. Alternatively, repurposing decommissioned open-pit lignite mines for PHS aligns with EU's JTM [3], which prioritises the economic revitalisation in coal regions in transition. Implementing PHS in former open-pit lignite mines, which are equipped with existing infrastructure, including roads, railways as well as electricity conversion and transmission systems, has the potential to significantly reduce the construction costs, which already benefit from the presence of at least one open-pit excavation to be repurposed into a storage reservoir. Additionally, this approach presents a viable solution to the predicament of site availability. Model projections for the EU power system emphasise that PHS total installed capacities need to increase by 18–20 GW to reach a total of 65 GW [31,33], constituting about 33% of the total 200 GW capacity required by 2030 (Fig. 1). The development of more large-scale energy storage projects is required to achieve these projections. While PHS accounts for over 90% of global storage capacity due to its scalability and lifespan of more than 50 years [34,35], batteries offer modularity and siting flexibility [36]. [37] propose a hybrid configuration of PHS and battery storage systems, as they exhibit complementary cost and performance characteristics, making them well-suited for synergistic roles in power systems. Hybrid pumped hydro–battery storage systems enable bidirectional energy exchange, potentially improving grid flexibility by allowing each technology to support the other during periods of low or negative electricity prices, and enhancing overall storage utilisation [37].

Current demonstration projects on PHS in open-pit mines

At international level, several projects have envisaged PHS implementation in former open-pit mines, such as the Kidston Pumped Storage Hydro Project led by Genex Power in North Queensland, Australia. The project proposes to demonstrate the beneficial reutilisation of the decommissioned Kidstone Gold Mine's infrastructure through the transformation of the mining pits into a 250 MW PHS power generation facility with a six-hour storage duration and an energy storage capacity exceeding 1.5 GWh to support grid stability in North Queensland [38].

Silvermines Hydro, situated in North Tipperary, Ireland, is another example of a project that aims to transform a closed open-pit mine within the Silvermines Mountains into a clean energy storage facility. This project aspires to align with Ireland's renewable energy objectives by providing up to 360 MW of power generation capacity and a daily storage capacity of up to 2.2 GWh [39]. The lower reservoir required for the PHS implementation already exists at the foot of the Silvermines Mountains in the form of the now flooded 70-m deep open-pit excavation. The project is designed to provide system services supporting renewable energy integration, aiming to enhance Ireland's energy infrastructure resilience and reduce carbon emissions, with a planned 2031 commissioning date [39].

The EU-funded ATLANTIS project established site-specific design criteria for PHS systems in open-pit mines to support the energy transition in coal regions in transition. Focusing on Greece's Kardias mine and Poland's Bełchatów-Szczerców complex, it demonstrated the technical [40], economic (112.33 M€ NPV, 5.65% return over 30 years; viable at modest price spreads of 37.28 €/MWh) [41], and socio-economic viability [32,42] of this transformation. Implementation at the Kardias mine is now underway [43,44]. Sustained policy support e.g. feed-in tariffs are required for a successful implementation [41]. This work demonstrates that repurposing open-pit mines for PHS is a viable approach supporting the energy transition, grid stability and sustainable utilisation of post-mining landscapes [14,32,42].

State-of-the-art in transforming open-pit mines into energy storage projects

Several investigations have been conducted to explore the prospects and challenges associated with transforming closed coal mines into PHS projects. These primarily focused on the challenges pertaining to potential groundwater contamination and geotechnical stability, underscoring the necessity for understanding and managing site-specific boundary conditions [45–51]. Other studies assessed the feasibility of integrating renewable resources with PHS systems using closed open-pit mines [52–56] as well as the economic feasibility [41,57–59]. Previous studies delineate the potentials of PHS both at a global scale and within the EU [27,28,58,60,61]. The respective assessments were predicated upon specific topological criteria and scenarios, such as the presence of a single or two water reservoirs.

The objective of the present study was to assess the potentials for PHS implementation in EU coal regions in transition by identifying suitable open-pit lignite mines for energy storage and overcoming overly optimistic volume estimates. Hereby, the approach employed is distinctive and aims to achieve a higher precision in the specific EU context. It integrates data from established mining databases within the EU, including geographical and volumetric data, mine depths and spatial extents, to precisely determine open-pit dimensions. Temporal variations over the 2015–2021 period are also included in the database applied [62]. As a consequence, the likelihood of errors in the identification of minor depressions and aquatic bodies that do not correspond to existing open-pit mines is ruled out in the present approach. Thus, a higher accuracy of storage potentials compared to previous studies has been established.

Materials and methods

Data acquisition

The first step in the present study was to create a digital database on EU open-pit lignite mines, utilising data primarily obtained from the European Environmental Bureau [62]. The database consists of 138 coal mines located in 16 European member states. The present study used the year 2021 as reference with a completeness of the mine depths and areas given with 69% and 58%, respectively, indicating the lack of data for other locations. These two parameters are among the key input parameters used in the dynamic mathematical model developed to calculate the energy storage and power capacity potentials, supplemented with additional data from other sources [63–66]. In the absence of information and publicly accessible datasets, e.g. for Romania, mine excavation depths were derived from the Copernicus DEM [67], which inherently contains vertical and horizontal uncertainties. This model is characterised by a horizontal grid spacing of 1.0 arc seconds, corresponding to a spatial resolution of about 30 m. The vertical accuracy of this DEM has a reported root mean square error (RMSE) of about ± 2 –4 m based on the topography [67]. Uncertainty ranges have not been included in the assessment of these mines. This suggests that the reported values for Romania should be interpreted with appropriate caution and viewed as estimations rather than definitive capacities. Data for the Greek mines were provided by the [53,68,69].

Key data elements within the created database include entities such as the administrative overview, geographical location, mine attributes including areas and depths, final pit lake volumes as well as references. The data underwent a comparative analysis with data sourced from additional origins (e.g. coal mine operators and existing databases) to ensure consistency. The list of available open-pit mines was evaluated against predefined criteria for selection and inclusion in the assessments [40]. The site selection methodology documented by [14] guided the adoption of key topographic, technical and proximity parameters in this study, ensuring technical robustness, consistency, and replicability. Fig. 2 shows the screening selection of the open-pit mines.

Here, the average slope of the reservoir embankments is a primary

Fig. 2. Screening flowchart for PHS site selection.

factor. A gently sloping or flat terrain facilitates the construction of a large-capacity reservoir, with a recommended range of 0–5° for the upper reservoir to limit excavation requirements, reduce construction costs and mitigate environmental disturbance [70–72]. The hydraulic head difference, defined by the elevation difference between the upper and lower reservoir water tables, directly influences the efficiency of energy generation and storage, i.e. the greater the hydraulic head between both reservoirs, the more power output can be achieved. The hydraulic head as well as generation and storage capacities are optimised for site-specific system designs [35]. Minimum hydraulic head requirements vary across different studies, typically ranging from 60 m to 300 m, with values of 150 m widely used in European assessments [61,70–72] and higher thresholds of up to 300 m applied in specific cases [73]. Minimising penstock lengths is recommended to optimise hydraulic efficiency by restricting flow velocities within design limits and avoiding erosion/cavitation in pressurised conduit [74]. Meanwhile, the maximum feasible tunnel length has evolved from conservative early limits of 5 km [70,71] to 20 km, a progression enabled by

improvements in tunnel construction (e.g. high performance liners reducing friction and turbulence inside penstocks) and transmission technologies, such as higher-voltage lines and lower-loss conductors that allow more efficient delivery of power over long distances [61,72]. Nonetheless, shorter penstocks, e.g. around 1,500 m as stated by [40,73] are preferred to minimise hydraulic head losses, construction costs, and environmental impacts, delivering an optimal trade-off between performance and costs. Collectively, these criteria ensure among others technical robustness, economic feasibility, and environmental sustainability of PHS installations in closed open-pit mines.

The assessment of PHS energy potentials in EU open-pit lignite mines was carried out through a hierarchical framework (Fig. 3). The theoretical storage capacity is the maximum amount of energy that the PHS system can absorb (Eq. (1), based on the site’s topography (i.e. elevation difference between both reservoirs and their volumes). The technical potential accounts for engineering and operational constraints, i.e. the installed power capacity, charge and discharge flow rates and durations, hydraulic losses and round trip efficiency, which reduce the theoretical capacity to a technically feasible level. The economic potential reflects the subset of technically viable options that could be developed to be cost-competitive with other energy sources under current or projected market and investment conditions. Finally, the realisable potential includes projects that are not only technically and economically feasible but also aligned with regulatory, environmental, social and implementation timelines, facilitating their implementation within short to medium time frame. However, technical, economic, and practical constraints progressively narrow this potential to determine the realisable potential. Applying these criteria, the investigation focused on open-pit mines exceeding 50 m in depth and 1 km² in surface area, using the technical constraints defined by [40] and [14]. Typical power capacities of PHS generally vary between 10 MW and 4,000 MW [75–78], while the EU does not impose any explicit minimum power installation standards. Nonetheless, every installation is subject to regional and environmental regulations, and aligns with the specific objectives of individual EU member states as outlined in the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) for the period 2021–2030 in accordance with the overarching EU energy and climate goals. Projects are generally designed to accommodate capacities that are both economically feasible and relevant to the electric grid. The prospective emphasis is on

Fig. 3. Potential pyramid illustrating the hierarchical levels of PHS storage potential. Theoretical and technical components are investigated in the course of the present potential assessment.

establishing utility-scale installations, mostly exceeding 100 MW, to ensure substantial benefits regarding energy storage and grid stabilisation. Smaller installations, typically those below 50 MW [79], are comparatively rare due to diminished economies of scale and their constrained influence on grid stability [80].

Model description

A dynamic mathematical model was developed to iteratively determine the feasible energy storage and power capacities by repurposing decommissioned open-pit lignite mines in the EU into PHS systems. The model integrates geospatial, topographical and hydraulic parameters derived from a comprehensive database of EU lignite mines (see Section 2.1) to calculate energy storage potentials, installed power capacities and volumetric flows derived from hydraulic losses across the system.

Potential energy storage (E_{PHS}) and installed power capacities (P) are calculated using Eqs. (1) and (2) with dynamic adjustments for reservoir geometry, hydraulic head difference variations, friction losses and system efficiency, thereby providing a more reliable estimation of technically feasible PHS potentials. The model allows for site-specific assessments that reflect the unique attributes of each mine. Table 1 summarises the key criteria and input parameters applied as boundary conditions in this research.

Calculation of PHS storage and power capacities

The geometry of a truncated cone is assumed as simplified open-pit lake volume based on the given area and depth data to standardise the assessment of all open-pits considered in the present study. The lower reservoir is the existing open-pit excavation, which is assumed to be flooded post-mining. The working water volume in the lower reservoir, cycled between the lower and upper reservoirs during operation, is quantified first to calculate the potential stored energy (E_{PHS}). A minimum water level of 10 m is defined to remain in the lower reservoir to limit erosion and sediment transport into the turbines and penstocks. An average embankment slope angle of 10° was adopted as a conservative assumption based on average slope angles of existing EU open-pit lignite mines. This metric is used for calculating the top minimum and working water levels in the lower reservoir, as well as the required penstock lengths. The volume of the upper reservoir and the average elevation difference between both reservoirs are calculated based on these data. E_{PHS} is directly proportional to the available working volume of the upper reservoir. Thus, E_{PHS} is expressed as a function of reservoir volume and hydraulic head difference by Eq. (1),

$$E_{PHS} = V_{Reservoir} \cdot \rho \cdot g \cdot \Delta h \tag{1}$$

where $V_{Reservoir}$ is the volume of the upper reservoir (m^3), ρ the density of water (kg/m^3), g the gravitational acceleration (m/s^2), and Δh the average hydraulic head difference between the upper and lower reservoirs (m). It is calculated as the average vertical distance between the centroid of the water column in both reservoirs during operation, rather than using a fixed maximum head to account for the non-linear relationship between stored volume and hydraulic head.

The relation between the installed PHS power and volumetric flow was determined iteratively for each site using Eq. (2),

$$P = \eta \cdot \rho \cdot Q \cdot g \cdot \Delta h \tag{2}$$

where P is the installed net power (MW), η the average PHS efficiency and Q the volumetric flow (m^3/s). The cycle efficiency of the system is influenced by a variety of factors, but generally ranges between 70% and 80% [84]. [16] estimate that generic energy losses attributable to pumping and discharging cycles are approximately 13.6% and 9.1%, respectively. Consequently, they deduce a total efficiency of 77.3% for a generic PHS installation. Energy losses that occur as water flows through the system due to friction, turbulence and other factors are considered using Eqs. 3–6. In this study, a total PHS efficiency of 78.6%, excluding 1.3% penstock losses for both pumping (0.5%) and discharging (0.8%) as discussed by [16] was assumed. Hydraulic losses in the penstock were calculated using the Darcy–Weisbach equation (Eq. (6)). For that purpose, the Reynolds number (Re) is accounted for according to Eq. (3).

$$Re = \frac{v \cdot d}{\mu} \tag{3}$$

where v is flow velocity (m/s), d is penstock internal diameter (m) assumed to be radial, and μ is the kinematic viscosity of water at 10°C and 101,325 Pa. Head loss was calculated with equations incorporating the relative penstock roughness (ϵ/d) and Re to obtain the Darcy friction factor (f_D), shown in Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively. Here, ϵ denotes the effective roughness of the penstock wall (mm) and D is the inner pipe diameter (m). Both the wall roughness and penstock length significantly impact frictional losses. [16] report an absolute roughness (ϵ) range of 0.5–1.5 mm for pressurised concrete water tunnels. In this case, an absolute roughness of 1.5 mm was applied to maintain a conservative assumption.

$$f_D = 0.0055 \left[1 + \left(\frac{2 \times 10^4 \epsilon \times 10^{-3}}{D} + \frac{10^6}{Re} \right)^{1/3} \right], \tag{4}$$

Total head loss (h_f) is given by:

$$h_f = S \cdot L, \tag{5}$$

where h_f is the head loss (m), L the penstock length (m), which is calculated as distance between the upper and lower reservoir water levels. Eq. (6) expresses h_f as a function of the penstock diameter D (m).

$$S = f_D \cdot \frac{8 Q^2}{\pi^2 g D^5}, \tag{6}$$

S denotes the hydraulic gradient, which when expressed through Darcy–Weisbach equation in terms of discharge Q , constitutes a dimensionless parameter (Eqs. (5) and (6)). The length of the penstock affects head losses due to friction and flow turbulences. In this study, the increase depends on the distance between the reservoirs and open-pit depths. Head losses as fundamental hydraulic parameters, excluding all external factors such as system design, component specifications and installation conditions, were considered in this research. Common PHS installations show typical total head loss percentages ranging from approximately 1% to 5% of the total head for both, pumping and discharging. The relative head loss excluding concentrated head losses, as one of the boundary conditions for this assessment was constrained to not exceed 5% to maintain a conservative approach.

The dynamic assessment model was used to calculate the working water volume in the reservoir, stored potential energy, volumetric flow and head losses for each site. Previous to the modelling activities discussed in the present study, the model has been verified against generic PHS data provided by [16] and a related case study for a Greek site by [41]. Maximum deviations in calculated net power capacities are below 2.1%, resulting from methodological differences in accounting for PHS pumping and generation efficiencies. The present study uses an average efficiency for both for simplicity, while [16] applied specific efficiencies

Table 1
Key technical criteria assumed for the lower reservoir in the present study.

Criteria	Criterion	Value	Unit
Theoretical	Minimum open pit depth	≥50	m
	Minimum open pit top areal size	≥1	km ²
Technical	Minimum power capacity	≥50	MW
	Maximum relative hydraulic head loss	<5	%
	Minimum water level in lower reservoir	10	m
	PHS round-trip efficiency	78.6	%

for pumping and generation as the study investigated a prospective PHS site with substantially more information was available than in the databases used here.

Storage application scenarios for PHS operation

Two scenarios designed to align with the operational dynamics of the EU electricity grid were evaluated, particularly in response to fluctuations between renewable energy surplus and peak demand periods. Both scenarios ensure that the identified PHS sites are of sufficient scale to serve as grid-supporting assets. Table 2 shows decision variables and constraints per scenario.

Scenario S_P: Maximisation of power capacity to support grid stability and economic benefit

This scenario requires a minimum installed power capacity of 50 MW and enforces a full daily pumping-generating cycle to align with diurnal electricity demand and variable renewable energy (vRES) fluctuations, prioritising grid stability and economic competitiveness. While PHS is technically capable of operation over a wide range of durations, its deployment is predominantly aligned with 24-hour charge–discharge cycles. This focus is driven by the dynamics of electricity market design, diurnal load patterns, and the associated economic incentives. The daily cycling pattern is a result of the discrepancy between electricity demand, which peaks during the day and the low-cost generation available at night. This enables PHS to arbitrage price differences by storing energy when electricity spot prices are low and producing electricity at high prices [41,81]. Day-ahead and real-time trading cycles in wholesale electricity spot markets further encourage this trend by establishing predictable price differences that support daily operations [82]. Additionally, PHS plants frequently provide ancillary services such as frequency regulation and spinning reserve, which are dispatched within the daily operational framework of power systems, further embedding them into 24-hour grid management routines [83]. Thus, the prevalence of daily cycling in PHS reflects economic and institutional drivers rather than technological constraints. The integration of 50 MW power threshold with 24-hour cycling ensures rapid grid-response while capturing wholesale price spreads, directly supporting the EU’s 2030–2050 vRES integration targets.

Scenario S_E: Maximisation of storage capacity to support grid stability in case of dunkelflaute events

This scenario maximises energy storage capacity to support grid stability during extended low-wind/solar periods (*dunkelflaute* events). Unlike Scenario S_P, which operates on a 24-hour daily cycle, S_E optimises for uninterrupted power supply by maximising the duration of power generation based on the maximum available storage capacity. At least 50 MW power capacity are maintained in this scenario to ensure eligibility for critical grid services like frequency containment reserves. The optimisation deliberately reduces Δh (Eq. (1)) within the given constraints to enable the facility to deliver uninterrupted ≥ 50 MW

Table 2
Scenario-specific constraints and key parameters.

	Scenario S _P	Scenario S _E
Objective	Maximise power capacity	Maximise energy storage capacity
Minimum power	≥ 50 MW	≥ 50 MW
Cycle time	≤ 24 h	Unconstrained (weeks)
Hydraulic head	Fixed at maximum site value	Optimised to maximise reservoir volume
Dispatch interpretation	Daily price arbitrage: pump during low-price periods (e.g. night) and generate during high-price peaks (e.g. day).	Continuous operation: dunkelflaute resilience, sustaining ≥ 50 MW over maximum time periods.

power during week-long *dunkelflaute* periods, e.g. a 8.4 GWh facility sustaining 50 MW for 168 h, bridging renewable supply gaps. This strategy directly enhances grid resilience against extended low-wind/solar events while addressing the EU’s need for cost-effective long-duration storage under 2030–2050 decarbonisation pathways.

Results and discussion

164 open-pit mines in the EU [62,64,65,68], were assessed to determine potential storage and power generation by means of the dynamic mathematical model. The number of suitable mines decreased with the application of the minimum depth and area criteria. Eventually, only 44 open-pit mines from the [62] database in ten European countries were considered for their potential storage and production capacities in the respective regions. In total, 50 open-pit lignite mines, which met the predefined criteria were investigated for their power generation and storage potentials in this study (Fig. 3). The hydraulic head difference calculated from the open-pit mine data varies from a low of 33 m to 440 m. The pits with low hydraulic head differences are defined by depths estimated at approximately 50 m, as documented in the databases used [62,63,65,66]. Only 40% of these mines conform to the criteria established by [28], which stipulates a threshold of hydraulic head difference exceeding 100 m.

While the operational status of the mines was not evaluated at this stage, initial review of available information suggested that the majority of the 50 mines investigated were operational, with only a very small number indicating possible non-operational status. This implies that even in the context of established post-mining strategies, the integration of PHS installations into the technical closure and future utilisation concepts of these open-pit mines could substantially contribute to the overarching objectives of decarbonisation and energy transition within the EU. This is relevant, since major cost savings are feasible when the lower reservoir is prepared for PHS operation before flooding [58].

Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate the existing energy storage and power capacities that have been installed, and the potential capacities that can be achieved by repurposing open-pit mines within the EU. Although greenfield PHS sites exist in the EU [15,27] show that applying a $L/\Delta h < 10$ viability threshold to [27] data, limits the exploitable potential to 40.3 TWh (Classes A-B, already developed) within the 60 TWh theoretical capacity, leaving about 35 TWh available from Classes C–E. Sites with lower $L/\Delta h$ ratios are regarded as technically suitable for development [70,85–87]. [15] further expanded their assessment to higher ratios with $L/\Delta h < 20$ as a maximum. This scenario reveals a significantly higher theoretical capacity, particularly within Classes C, D, and E (about 230 TWh), although these categories are associated with higher costs and reduced economic feasibility [27]. Overall, this suggests that, while the EU possesses considerable untapped topographical and technical potential for new reservoirs, their development is currently constrained by economic limitations, possible environmental impacts and public opposition.

Maximising power capacity versus maximising storage capacity

PHS energy storage potentials across two scenarios with divergent power and energy storage capacity assumptions were evaluated (Figs. 5 and 6). Power capacities differ significantly between both scenarios: S_P totals 10.5 GW_{net}, while S_E amounts to 6.1 GW_{net}, representing a 42% lower aggregate power capacity. Fig. 4 shows the maximum achievable capacity per scenario, obtained by combining the current installed PHS capacity [15] with scenario-specific potential additions. Here, Germany demonstrates the highest power capacity potential of 9.5 GW_{net}, while Hungary shows the highest relative growth opportunity with a potential power capacity of 2.3 GW in S_P.

Notably, energy storage capacity in S_E increases substantially to 12.76 TWh compared to 128 GWh in S_P, reflecting the impact of the underlying assumptions for energy storage maximisation (Fig. 5). This

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of open-pit lignite mines investigated for the EU27 and its prospective member states with their potential power and storage capacities (1: S_P, 2: S_E).

difference arises because S_E specifically optimises storage capacity for long-duration resilience (e.g. mitigating *dunkelflaute* events), whereas S_P prioritises grid stability via 24-hour cycling, leveraging price arbitrage during renewable surplus and peak demands. The potential to expand existing reservoirs or construct new ones, particularly under S_E can significantly enhance grid flexibility, reduce renewable energy curtailment, and better support the integration of vRES by repurposing suitable open-pit mines into high-hydraulic head PHS. However, S_P highlights the feasibility of smaller-scale PHS applications, which may be more practical in settings with very limited (hydro-)geological or spatial constraints.

Scenario S_P: Maximisation of power capacity to support grid stability and economic benefit

In total, an energy storage potential of 117 GWh and about 9.6 GW installed power can be realised by implementing PHS in EU27 open-pit lignite mines, which will be closed by the end of the next decade (Fig. 4). This corresponds to an increase of about 20% of the currently installed PHS power and >45% of its current storage capacities. With additional technically feasible power capacities of about 0.9 GW from Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia as EU membership candidate states, approximately 5% of the 200 GW energy storage capacity that the EU aims to achieve by 2030 [17] can be realised from implementing PHS in decommissioned open-pit mines. In S_P, the aggregate installed capacity

of the ten examined countries amounts to 10.5 GW of potential power, while the stored energy capacity is at 128 GWh (Figs. 5 and 6). The spatial distribution is highly uneven, with Germany contributing the largest share of both power (3.3 GW) and storage (40.2 GWh), i.e. more than 30% of the total estimated potential power production and storage capacities of the EU27. This is due to the fact that Germany hosts deeper open-pit mines compared to other EU countries, e.g. the Hambach and Fortuna-Gasdorf mines reaching depths of up to 450 m and 360 m, respectively. Thus, an increase by almost 50% in installed power and more than 100% in storage capacities is feasible by PHS implementation in German open-pit lignite mines.

Greece, Romania, Poland and Czech Republic also significantly contribute to the additional energy storage potentials that can be attained in the EU27, accounting for 18%, 18%, 17% and 9%, respectively. As introduced before, the accuracy of the calculated power and energy storage capacities for Romania (1.7 GW and 20.7 GWh, respectively) is uncertain due to the use of DEM data [67]. The combined potential storage capacities of Greece, Romania, Poland and Czech Republic mines represent approximately 62% of the total capacities of the EU. This underscores the significant untapped potential which can be exploited by installing PHS in open-pit mines. Bulgaria, Hungary, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia contribute only marginal energy reservoirs (<=10 GWh). A detailed assessment of the energy storage capacities in Bulgaria is not depicted from the presented results

Fig. 5. Currently installed PHS power capacities [2] and potential power capacities (GW) that can be realised in the EU for both scenarios. (*) – prospective EU member states. Country-specific storage potentials are detailed in Table 3.

Fig. 6. Currently available energy storage capacities in the EU [2] and potential storage capacities that can be realised from the investigated lignite open-pit mines for both scenarios. (*) – prospective EU member states. Country-specific storage potentials are detailed in Table 3.

due to a lack of data. Even though low potentials based on one open-pit mine in Bulgaria with known information were calculated, an increase of 90% in Bulgaria’s currently installed PHS capacities can be realised. An extensive data collection in collaboration with national authorities, including ministries responsible for energy management within respective countries will facilitate the utilisation of more detailed data pertinent to each individual country. Table 3 presents the currently installed power capacities, available energy storage capacities and their potential increase by PHS implementation in closed open-pit mines in the EU.

Scenario S_E : Maximisation of storage capacity to support grid stability in case of dunkelflaute events

Nearly all sites except for one meet the ≥ 50 MW net-power constraint. Net-power refers to the remaining power after accounting for all losses calculated by means of net efficiency. In S_E , the overall power capacity is reduced to 6.1 GW, while energy storage capacity is significantly increased to 12.76 TWh (Figs. 5 and 6). This represents almost a factor of 50 increase in the current EU energy storage capacity of 259 GWh when all assessed mines are included (Table 3). The amplification is primarily contributed by large-scale reservoirs in Germany (6.0 TWh), Poland (3.6 TWh), Romania (0.7 TWh) and Greece (1.4 TWh) as

Table 3

Current and calculated power production and energy storage potentials per EU member and candidate state ([15,25,90]. S_P : Maximisation of power capacity to support grid stability and economic benefits; S_E : Maximisation of storage capacity to support grid stability in case of dunkelflaute events.

Country	Currently available PHS capacities		Additional potential energy capacities			
	Installed power (GW)	Energy storage (GWh)	Power (GW)		Energy storage (GWh)	
			S_P	S_E	S_P	S_E
Bulgaria	1.4	41.7	0.1	0.09	1.3	120
Czech Republic	1.2	5.7	0.9	0.5	11.0	707
Germany	6.2	38.0	3.3	1.9	40.2	6033
Greece	0.7	5.1	1.8	1.1	21.2	1353
Hungary	0	–	2.3	0.2	2.7	56.0
Poland	1.8	18.0	1.6	0.8	20.0	3597
Romania	0.9	21.1	1.7	1.0	20.7	724
Montenegro*	0.3	–	0.06	0.06	0.7	2.2
North Macedonia*	0	–	0.07	0.07	0.8	5.5
Serbia*	0.6	–	0.8	0.5	9.2	158
EU capacities	46.1 GW	259 GWh				
Total EU potentials			9.6	5.4	117	12,590
Total calculated potentials including EU membership candidates *			10.5	6.1	128	12,755

presented the quantitative breakdowns in Fig. 6 and Table 3. Consequently, these four countries account for 94% of the storage capacity calculated in this scenario, representing an increase by a factor of 45 above the current EU PHS capacity.

The capacity values presented in this assessment diverge from prior European studies [15,28,61], with [28] representing the most recent assessment of existing storage potentials, contingent upon the criteria and input data used. The potential calculated for Scenario S_E is approximately three times larger than the maximum theoretical one identified by [61] for interconnected reservoirs, i.e. 4 TWh for interconnections up to 20 km, highlighting the advantage of re-using existing open-pit mines.

The S_E capacity for the mines in ten countries investigated here is 2.2 times larger than reported by [28], a divergence primarily stemming from methodological differences where high volume reservoirs over power capacities was prioritised. In this scenario, the hydraulic head was significantly reduced to maximise the storage capacities. Further, technical criteria, which include the consideration of maximum reservoir volumes and net head differences, have been applied in the present calculations. Specifically, the total lower reservoir volume was not used, as a minimum of 10 m is consistently maintained for operational reasons. Further distinctions arise from the integration of reliable excavation dimensions (mine depths, spatial extents, and volumes) sourced from well-established databases and topographical data derived from DEMs. The use of DEMs offers considerable benefits; however, it is accompanied by several limitations, including resolution constraints, interpolation artefacts and potential georeferencing errors leading to either overestimation or underestimation of the actual results. Additionally, DEMs often face challenges to accurately represent steep terrain features particularly relevant to open-pit mine assessments [88,89]. In contrast, [15] report a substantially lower technically feasible EU-wide storage capacity of 2.3 TWh from existing PHS, with only 500–600 GWh considered realisable under practical constraints. S_P estimates a technical potential for new PHS projects of approximately 130 GWh aligning with the existing realisable range reported by [15], whereas S_E projects about 13 TWh, exceeding all prior site-specific assessments, including [28]. The technical assessment presented here suggests possible storage capacities that could complement European energy transition efforts, though economic viability, grid integration requirements, and local implementation challenges would ultimately

determine the practical contribution of these systems.

Limitations of the present study and recommendations for future work

Given that the primary source databases [62,64,65,90] lack complete coverage of the key parameters, such as mine areas and depths, this study's calculations on power installation and energy storage potentials are subject to uncertainties. Additional data were obtained from secondary sources to address existing gaps. Future work should prioritise acquiring missing data and updating existing datasets through direct engagement with mine operators, mining authorities and review of historical data to establish an even more reliable quantification basis. When employing DEMs, conducting sensitivity analyses across multiple DEM sources and different resolution levels, particularly when high resolution DEMs are unavailable, will enhance estimate reliability. Our analysis indicates that the aggregate potential energy storage capacity of all EU27 open-pit lignite mines is insufficient to single-handedly facilitate the EU's 2030 climate goals. However, non-lignite open-pit mines could meaningfully augment this potential. The next step will thus integrate this approach with complementary hybrid solutions (e.g. battery-PHS hybrids) to expand feasible energy storage capacity. This study estimates the technical potential of repurposing 50 decommissioned EU lignite mines for PHS at approximately 130 GWh (S_P) and 12.76 TWh (S_E) of energy storage capacity, alongside with 10.5 GW and 6.1 GW of installed power capacity, respectively (Table 2). However, these figures exclude economic viability, grid integration costs, as well as regulatory and environmental constraints, which are all critical factors for practical implementation. Geotechnical uncertainties may affect long-term reservoir integrity. Therefore, site-specific stability analyses are recommended. A dynamic techno-economic assessment should evaluate the economic viability of repurposing the identified EU open-pit mines technically suitable for PHS, incorporating environmental constraints to identify optimal sites, especially for high-hydraulic head systems ($\Delta h > 100$ m). Of particular interest are 23 mines requiring detailed assessment for such applications.

Conclusions

Additionally feasible power production and energy storage capacities in the EU27 and its membership candidate states with existing open-pit lignite mines were determined by applying a dedicated dynamic mathematical model and dedicated a mine database. The main energy storage technology in the EU is currently and by far PHS [13]. However, the key challenge for the implementation of this technology are mainly geographical constraints which can be addressed by repurposing closed open-pit lignite mines. 50 out of 147 open-pit coal mines in Europe fulfil the theoretical and technical criteria defined for this assessment. Repurposing 50 closed EU lignite mines for PHS could add 9.6–5.4 GW power and 117–12,590 GWh storage capacities (scenarios S_P and S_E , respectively). S_P increases the current EU energy storage potentials by 45%, which is significant for managing daily vRES fluctuations. S_E , with a 4,860% increase in storage capacities, enables large-scale seasonal energy shifting, supporting the grid's energy supply during *dunkelflaute* events. The EU possesses a technical potential for PHS, which encompasses the capacity that can be realised by leveraging existing technological progress, independent of economic factors. The successful deployment of PHS systems in these areas could serve as a blueprint for other mining regions in transition worldwide, supporting the global goals of decarbonisation and energy transition [12].

Realising the full potential of repurposed open-pit lignite mines for PHS demands targeted technological advances. A comprehensive geotechnical assessment and continuous monitoring is essential for ensuring slope stability, particularly in deep, non-uniform excavations where post-mining subsidence or seismic activity could threaten reservoir integrity. Innovative barrier mechanisms, including impermeable membranes and geochemical remediation strategies, are crucial to

prevent leaching of legacy pollutants (e.g., heavy metals, sulfates) from the lower reservoir into adjacent groundwater aquifers during operational cycles. Turbulent flow dynamics in large, irregular pit lakes necessitate computational fluid dynamics simulations to optimise penstock geometry and minimise energy losses from transient flow conditions. Finally, erosion mitigation strategies, including bio-engineered embankments, sediment traps, and adaptive flow control, are required to protect penstock intakes and reservoir edges from accelerated wear during high-frequency pumping cycles. Prioritising research and development in these areas will bridge the gap between technical feasibility and deployment, enabling scalable, environmentally-friendly PHS integration within post-mining landscapes.

Typically, the areas adjacent to open-pit coal mining operations offer substantial tracts of land, which are generally deemed less suitable for alternative uses, rendering them available for the installation of photovoltaic and wind farms, in addition to providing convenient access to on-site storage facilities. The integration of PHS systems with the presence of such renewable energy sources in mining regions transitioning to sustainable energy practices presents a promising pathway for enhancing energy security, stability, and efficiency. Integrating the PHS technology with renewable energy sources through the use of closed open-pit mines investigated in this study, contributes to achieving the EU climate goals, as the energy transition in European coal regions is mainly driven by the EU climate goals, economic diversification needs, and environmental imperatives. By effectively storing surplus solar and wind resources, former mining regions will not only reduce their carbon footprint, but also contribute to a more efficient, reliable and sustainable energy system, while mitigating energy transmission losses typically associated with centralised power generation and long-distance transmission. However, PHS alone cannot meet the EU storage targets. Therefore, additional utility-scale power production and storage capacities are required to reach the 100% renewable energy target by 2050 [91,92]. Hybrid solutions, e.g. hybrid PHS and battery storage systems [37], using high water pressure to store energy on the seabeds of deep lakes and oceans for scalable long duration storage with minimal environmental footprint [93] and complementary technologies including compressed air energy storage (CAES) in depleted hydrocarbon reservoirs or solution-mined salt caverns [94–96], hydrogen storage in pressurised vessels, cryogenic tanks, or geological formations (saline aquifers, depleted reservoirs) coupled with electrolyzers and fuel cell/turbine systems [97–99], Power-to-Gas-to-Power using methanation to convert excess electricity to synthetic methane stored in natural gas infrastructure [100,101] and the use of subsurface mines for gravity-based energy storage [102,103] are required.

Policymakers should facilitate the sustainable implementation of PHS in transitioning EU coal regions by streamlining permitting processes through early engagement of multi-disciplinary expertise (geotechnics, hydrogeology, engineering, and socio-economics) to mitigate project delays and costs. Concurrently, market regulations require clarification regarding ownership structures, equitable grid access, and compensation mechanisms for ancillary services to enhance economic viability. Substantial financial incentives, including subsidies, grants, low-interest loans, and targeted tax exemptions or rebates, are essential to mitigate high capital expenditure and attract private investment. Comprehensive environmental risk assessments, integrating detailed geotechnical stability analyses and hydrological impact evaluations with continuous monitoring protocols, must be mandated to ensure sustainable implementation with minimal adverse effects. Furthermore, proactive community engagement strategies, encompassing information dissemination, education, workforce re-skilling programmes, and tangible regional benefits such as job creation and infrastructure upgrades, are crucial for fostering public acceptance. Strategic land-use planning should integrate PHS projects to resolve conflicts and optimise multi-purpose reservoir benefits through cost-benefit modelling. Increased research and development funding at national and EU levels is

required for pilot and demonstration projects to validate technological innovations, improve efficiency, and reduce costs. Finally, advocacy for clear and consistent investment criteria within the EU Taxonomy Climate Delegated Act is necessary to support hydropower investments. These integrated actions will unlock PHS potentials for enhancing EU energy security, grid stability, and renewable energy integration.

Although decommissioning of lignite coal mines presents opportunities for utility-scale energy storage projects, the transformation process may also raise socio-economic challenges such as job losses, reduced income levels and limited opportunities for reskilling of employees in alternative sectors as most of these regions depend entirely on coal. Therefore, a successful transition requires region-specific strategies, including transparent communication, stakeholder involvement, and targeted investment in workforce adaptation and infrastructure [32,42]. In this context, integrating risk management into broader land use planning is substantial in achieving a balance between technical feasibility, environmental protection and social acceptance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Priscilla Ernst: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Thomas Kempka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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